

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP AND COMPARISON OF A THERMAL LOAD MODEL FOR LIVESTOCK BARN

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ABSTRACT

Intensive livestock farming stands out as an energy-demanding sector within agriculture. Despite this, precise hourly temporal information regarding on-farm energy use – both in terms of quantity and fuel source – is not available. This information is needed for evaluating and comparing scenarios using renewable technologies like heat pumps, photovoltaics, small wind turbines, etc. As such, a modelling approach tailored to one pig farm in Belgium, was developed in 2022 to derive hourly heating and cooling loads. To calculate these loads, the model assumes a quasi-steady state energy balance, taking into account the building's properties, animal occupation numbers (including their respective age and environmental needs), and outside temperature and relative humidity. The model predicts a total heat load of 212 MWh per year, an underestimation of 4 % compared to the average use of the barn (220 MWh). In this work, the same model is tested against physical measurements on the pig farm, using a transportable experimental set-up by means of an ultrasonic flow rate meter and temperature sensors at the inlet and outlet pipes of the heating circuit. These measurements were performed during three non-consecutive weeks: one in spring 2021, summer 2023, and winter 2024. Respectively for each period, the thermal model overestimates the measured load by 80 %, 10 % and 3 %, but with local outliers reaching up to 700 %. In the next steps, the thermal load model will be improved upon and expanded to include electrical loads as well. Eventually, the model can be applied to other farms in Belgium and validated with the transportable set-up.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) recently reported that the livestock sector contributes 12 % to the total global greenhouse gas emissions (FAO 2023). Up to 7.6 % is found to be related to direct on-farm energy use. Only 4 % of this on-farm energy demand is being obtained from renewable energy sources (Costantino, Calvet, and Fabrizio 2023). On top of that, volatility in prices of livestock products often mirrors oil prices, indicating a high share of fossil fuels in livestock farming (FAO 2021). This use of fossil fuels in livestock farming is backed-up by a local survey among pig farmers performed by ILVO in 2021, showing that 29 out of 38 participants (76 %) still use fuel oil to heat their farms (Everaert et al. 2023). Identifying energy intensive processes and how much energy they require, will help in the research to integrate measures on energy efficiency or RES and therefore reduce the emissions from direct energy use.

Paris et al. (Paris et al. 2022) revealed a significant variation in the on-farm energy requirements for the production of different livestock products. One kg of energy-corrected cow milk requires 0.54 – 1.76 MJ on-farm energy use, beef requires 9.36 – 31.97 MJ/kg, pork 2.6 – 11.1 MJ/kg, poultry meat 0.5 – 6.6 MJ/kg, and chicken eggs 0.6 – 10.3 MJ/kg. So, which processes exactly contribute to this energy demand and make this quantification so difficult?

A literature study assessed the contributors to on-farm energy use for pig, poultry, and cow barns (Costantino et al. 2016). In pig barns, 47.7 % of the total electricity need goes to ventilation and additional localised heating for piglets (heat lamps), followed by 18.7 % for feeding and water circulation, 11.3 % for feed preparation, and the rest for manure handling. The thermal needs of pig barns include 69.2 % for general heating of the barn environment, and 29.5 % for manure disposal. For broilers, the ventilation takes up 39.5 % of the electrical needs, while general heating requires 96.3 % of all thermal needs. Laying hens do not have thermal requirements, except for manure handling. There, the biggest energy requirements are electrical and include 43.7 % for ventilation and 15.2 % for artificial lighting to induce multiple day-night cycles per day. Finally, in dairy barns 33.3 % of the electricity is needed for milking robots including feeding, 20 % for ventilation, 12 % for milk cooling, and 18.2 % for manure treatment (Costantino et al. 2016). In dairy barns, no thermal energy is used for the barn environmental control. Barber et al. (1988) and Hörndahl (2008) reported similar findings. The efficiency of these installations and their maintenance, as well as different building properties (e.g. ventilation strategies, openings in the building envelope etc.) could explain this range in reporting (Costantino and Fabrizio 2019).

In the residential and commercial sector, strong regulations are already enforced on the energetic performance of buildings. This is reported by means of an Energy Performance Certificate (EPC), submissive to standardised measurement methodologies. No such methodologies and regulations exist on the energetic performance of livestock barns, aside from ventilation standards (ErP Directive 2009/125/EC). Recently, Costantino and Fabrizio (2023) published a new standardised method to assess the energetic performance in livestock barns. Their publication will help research, including this one, towards a better and more unified quantification of energy use in livestock farming.

To quantify direct energy use in the residential and commercial sector, building energy simulation models (BES-models) are already widely used (Harish and Kumar 2016). A BES-model uses physics-based mathematical models to, given a set of boundary conditions and inputs, calculate different variables such as energy loads, indoor climate conditions etc. (Costantino 2023). The restrictions set on the EPC are often used as boundary conditions in BES-models, explaining their popularity in the residential and commercial sector. For livestock barns, there are few simulation approaches reported in literature. Only a total of 42 relevant papers were identified by a systematic literature review performed in July 2023 (Costantino 2023). Before 2015, no more than 15 papers were published on this subject. As from 2020, the subject gained traction, indicating its growing relevance. The simulation models are, however, custom made and always tailored to one particular case study. While CFD has been emerging as simulation methods for the air flow in ventilated barns, it is slow and might be too complex to merely assess the energetic performance of a barn. The EPC proposal of Costantino et al. (Costantino and Fabrizio 2023) is a good starting point, but only provides a general notion of the energy use and no detailed load profile.

Another aspect lacking as reported by Costantino et al. (Costantino 2023), is experimental validation of BES-models. Most of the models merely compare the simulated indoor temperatures and relative humidities, due to limited data availability on energy use at a farm level. Model validity can be performed in two ways: operationally (does the model agree with the observed data?) and conceptually (do the assumptions and the implemented theories make sense?) (Kerr and Goethel 2014).

In this research work, an experimental measuring method to validate a thermal load model, developed in 2022 by Faes et al. (Faes et al., 2022), will be presented on the case study of a pig barn in Belgium. The set-up could be used to validate thermal BES-models applied to other farms as well.

The methodology proposed in this work, serves as a first step to build and validate a scalable BES-model that can estimate hourly heating (and cooling) loads and electricity loads of a barn using general input data such as the building's size and properties, animal occupation, weather conditions, and so on. Being able to estimate hourly energy loads with BES-models, is a crucial step towards simulating the integration potential of renewable energy sources.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Simulation method

Within ILVO and Ghent University (UGent), a multi-zone quasi-steady state BES-model tailored to one specific pig farm in Melle (Belgium) was developed by Faes et al. (Faes et al., 2022). This simulation model estimates hourly heat requirements for the barn, solving an hourly heat balance. For each compartment, a zone is implemented for which the heat balance is formulated and solved.

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{load}} [W] = \dot{Q}_{\text{animal}} - \dot{Q}_{\text{conduction}} - \dot{Q}_{\text{infiltration}} - \dot{Q}_{\text{ventilation}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{floor}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{lamps}} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

These terms represent the required heating load to meet the pigs' ideal heat conditions (\dot{Q}_{load}), the heat rejected from the animals (\dot{Q}_{animal}) (Forcada and Abecia 2019), conduction ($\dot{Q}_{\text{conduction}}$) and infiltration ($\dot{Q}_{\text{infiltration}}$) losses through the building envelope, heat losses due to ventilation ($\dot{Q}_{\text{ventilation}}$), heat provided from underfloor heating (\dot{Q}_{floor}) and heat lamps (\dot{Q}_{lamps}) for localised heating in the barn. Input parameters entail weather conditions (air temperature and relative humidity), properties of the building envelope, and the animal occupation per zone. For more information, the authors refer to the work of Faes et al. (Faes et al., 2022).

They published some preliminary results and a first validation of the model. Monthly energy readings from an analog gas meter were compared to the simulated results. Their findings indicated a correct order of magnitude of the monthly uses, but with an overall underestimation of the measured loads.

A steady state model is a good basis for assessing total energy loads in the design phase of a building, but is not necessarily ideal when comparing it to real-life operation (Costantino and Fabrizio 2019). This statement will be further evaluated by testing the current model against experimental data.

Furthermore, the current model is limited to evaluate thermal loads only.

2.2 Case study and experimental set-up

The abovementioned pig farm is called the "Varkenscampus", a farrow-to-finish commercial pig barn of ILVO, UGent and HoGent. The farm is connected to an electricity and natural gas grid and has a 60-kW gas boiler (ATAG XL70). On average it houses 119 sows, 366 piglets, 463 fattening pigs and two boars. The yearly heating loads consist of 220 MWh natural gas and 920 liter fuel oil used to fuel one space heater (AcroTherm EC 85), while the total electricity load is around 115 MWh (mostly to cover the ventilation requirements, lights, and feeding pumps). Within the farm, two heating circuits operate at different setpoint temperatures. One circuit maintains a low temperature (LT) of 40 °C to provide underfloor heating for the piglets, the other operates at a higher temperature (HT) of 60 °C for domestic hot water and air preheaters. Currently, the boiler provides water at 60 °C, which is then mixed with cold water to achieve the desired 40 °C. Heating in the farm is provided through air preheaters (twin tubes) in three nursery compartments, four fattening compartments and throughout the main corridor of the other twelve fattening compartments. This is regulated by means of a Hotraco climate computer, based on the animal occupation inside each compartment. For two farrowing and three nursery compartments, additional underfloor heating is present. These are manually turned on or off by the farm manager by means of individual valves, dependent on the age of the piglets. The remaining four compartments and boar pen do not require any heating. Heat lamps, and additionally the space heater during winter, provide additional heating for newborn piglets.

During three non-consecutive periods, temperatures and flow rates were measured in five-minute intervals. The first period took place in spring 2021, from the 30th of March until the 7th of April. The second one in summer 2023, from the 25th of June until the 1st of July. The third period took place during winter 2024, from the 7th until the 14th of February. Measurements were made in five-minute intervals on the thermal system of the barn. The flow rates in the LT and HT circuits are measured using two individual ultrasonic flow rate sensors and logged with the Fluxus-F601 measuring device (Flexim, Germany). The flow rate sensors have a reported accuracy of +/- 0.3 %. Additionally, four temperature

sensors (TMC6-HD) and loggers (HOBO onset datalogger h08-004-02) are used to measure the supply and return temperature of the two circuits. These have an accuracy between ± 0.2 °C in a temperature range of 0 to 70 °C. However, this is dependent on the used logger and is not reported for our logger. Therefore, the accuracy was set to ± 0.5 °C. The sensors are represented in Figure 1, and the experimental set-up is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Sensors used to measure the heating loads of the case study with (a) the temperature sensor (TMC6-HD) and HOBO datalogger (h08-004-02) and (b) the flow rate logger with two ultrasonic sensors (Fluxus-F601).

Figure 2: Temperature sensors (T) and flow rate sensors (F) used to measure two different heating circuits: the total heating circuit of the barn (high temperature (HT) at 60 °C) and the underfloor heating (low temperature (LT) at 40 °C) which is regulated with a mixing valve (black arrow).

The heat transfer to each circuit towards the barn can then be calculated from the obtained flow rate \dot{V} (liter/hour) and temperatures T_{in} and T_{out} (in °C).

$$\dot{Q}[W] = \dot{m} \left[\frac{kg}{s} \right] \left(h(T_{in}) \left[\frac{J}{kg} \right] - h(T_{out}) \left[\frac{J}{kg} \right] \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

with

$$\dot{m} \left[\frac{kg}{s} \right] = \dot{V} \left[\frac{l}{h} \right] \rho(T_{in}) \left[\frac{kg}{m^3} \right] 10^{-3} \left[\frac{m^3}{l} \right] 3600^{-1} \left[\frac{h}{s} \right]$$

Here, \dot{m} is the mass flow rate, h the enthalpy, and ρ the density of the heating fluid (water). The accuracy on \dot{Q} is determined from error propagation on the measured flow rate $\delta\dot{V}$ and temperatures δT .

$$\delta\dot{Q} = |\dot{Q}| \sqrt{\left(\frac{\delta\dot{m}}{\dot{m}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sqrt{\delta h_{in}^2 + \delta h_{out}^2}}{h_{in} - h_{out}} \right)^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

with

$$\delta\dot{m} = |\dot{m}| \sqrt{\left(\frac{\delta\dot{V}}{\dot{V}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta\rho}{\rho} \right)^2} ; \quad \delta\rho(T) = \left| \left(\frac{\partial\rho}{\partial T} \right)_p (T) \right| \delta T \quad \text{and} \quad \delta h(T) = \left| \left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial T} \right)_p (T) \right| \delta T$$

The relative difference between measurements and simulation results are calculated as follows and represented by means of a box plot.

$$\text{relative difference} = \frac{\text{experimental data} - \text{simulated data}}{\text{experimental data}} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

3 RESULTS

During the measuring periods, hourly outside temperatures were obtained from Solcast (Bright 2019). These were also used as input for the simulation model and are represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Outdoor air temperatures measured during the measuring periods and used as input for the simulation model as obtained from Solcast (Bright 2019).

3.1 Temperature and flow rate measurements

In Figure 4, the obtained hourly temperature and flow rates are represented by means of a moving average window. The accuracy of the sensors is indicated as well but remain relatively small.

In the three seasons a clear difference between the temperature regimes of both underfloor heating and total circuits can be observed. The total circuit operates between 60 and 70 °C, while the underfloor circuit operates between a 30 and 40 °C regime. To reach the lower temperature, hot water from the boiler is mixed with the return water by means of a three-way valve (indicated with an arrow on Figure 2) and additional cold domestic water. The setpoint (or supply) temperatures of both circuits remain relatively constant for all seasons, while the difference between the supply and return temperatures is smaller during warm weather and bigger during cold outdoor temperatures.

As shown in Figure 4, the flow rate of the underfloor heating exhibits a relatively constant behaviour. This is dependent on the occupation rate of piglets requiring underfloor heating inside the barn and is regulated by manual valves. The farm manager opens or closes these manually based on the compartment occupancy, which explains the step-like behaviour. This also explains the switch in supply- and return temperatures during the first days of the summer measurements (Figure 4b). As the temperature of the supply is measured above the three-way mixing valve, heat from the total circuit rises up to reach the sensor, even though no flow is present.

A final observation is the more fluctuating behaviour of the total circuit. These measurements include heat provided for the air preheaters, as regulated by a Hotraco climate computer, and sanitary hot water. This latter is used for showering of sows and people. Every three weeks, 16 sows have to be washed before entering the farrowing compartment and every human entering the barn has to take a shower to prevent spreading of diseases.

3.2 Comparison between experimental and simulated heat transfer rates

The calculated heat transfer rates and simulation results are shown in Figure 5, again for the three different measurement seasons. The y-ranges are fixed for the separate heating circuits.

The error margins on the measured heat transfers, due to the limited sensor accuracy, are shown as well. On average, the absolute error on the underfloor heating circuit is +/- 1.3 kW and for the total circuit +/- 1.9 kW. The accuracy of the temperature sensors is the main cause of this error margin, as they provide the enthalpy of the supply and return temperatures. According to the calculation (Eq. 2), this difference decides the exchanged heat, therefore obtaining a smaller quantity but with double the error margin. The relative difference between the simulated data and measurements are represented in Figure 6.

First, the results of the floor heating are discussed. During spring (Figure 5a) and winter times (Figure 5b), the simulation represents the overall average of the actual floor heating. The temporary fluctuations are not taken into account. These fluctuations could be caused by piglet activity in the barn, the exact occupation of the piglets or external weather fluctuations. Piglet activity could for example influence the potential of the underfloor heating to transfer its heat. As for the occupation numbers, the model assumes average values when a compartment is considered full or empty, when in reality this depends on the amount of piglets born. Weather fluctuations, such as wind speed and solar radiation on the building envelope could influence the measured variations as well, but are omitted in the simulation model.

During summer period (Figure 5c), the simulation model overestimates the total underfloor heat demand by as much as 227 %. This is explained by the farm manager manually closing valves for some of the compartments, as it reached 30 °C during the first 3 days of the measurements. The simulation model does not take this into account, as it works with a fixed animal occupation cycle to estimate the underfloor heat demand.

Figure 4: Hourly supply and return temperatures, and flow rates for the underfloor heating circuit (LT) and the total heating circuit (HT) during one week in (a) spring, (b) summer, and (c) winter, accuracies are indicated but are small compared to the measured values.

Figure 5: Heat transfer rate for the underfloor heating circuit (LT) and total heating circuit (HT) measured data compared to simulated data from the building energy simulation model (a) during spring 2021 (b) during summer 2023 and (c) during winter 2024.

Second, the total heating circuit is discussed. During the spring month in 2021, the trends in the simulated data are caused by the model's visible dependence on the outside temperature. This trend can be seen in the measured exchanged heat as well, but less consistently. Other weather conditions, as mentioned before, were not taken into account in the simulation model and could explain this behaviour. During the summer month in 2023, there is seemingly an agreement, but it is actually a false one. The simulated total heat includes underfloor heating, which was overestimated. The model assumes that there is almost no high temperature heat demand during summer, and underestimates this high temperature demand by 80%. This is a false assumption by not taking into account showers. During the first three days, the flow rate inside the underfloor circuit was zero. As there was probably no need for air heaters either, the fluctuations in the measured data could be related to shower use. Showers are not taken into account in the model, explaining why this demand is underestimated. During the winter period of 2024, the model seems to agree most with the measured data, as can be seen in Figure 6 as well. The variations, again, closely represent the relation with the external air temperature.

Figure 6: Relative difference between the simulated results and the measurements, a negative deviation implies an overestimation by the simulation while a positive difference implies an underestimation.

In total, the underfloor heating circuit contributes to 46 % of the total heat measured during all periods. In the simulated results, this contribution is 63.8 %, probably related to the disagreement during the summer period.

It can be concluded that the BES-model is able to mirror the behaviour of the hourly heating loads of the barn, but not on a quantitative level. It is performing even worse for warm weather conditions. Further research is needed to investigate the dependence of the simulated heat demand on other external factors, such as weather conditions and exact animal occupation numbers. That way, these could be integrated into the BES-model as well to improve its behaviour.

In the future, this model could be used to estimate the heating loads for other barns, in order to simulate the influence of renewable energy sources. By means of a transportable set-up, as described in section 2.2, similar measurements can be conducted on-site and be used as validation for the thermal load model.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this paper presents a comparative analysis between a building energy simulation model and experimental measurements on an hourly level, aimed at deriving precise temporal information about on-farm heat loads in intensive livestock farming. The insights gained from this model, together with electricity loads, should provide valuable input data to simulate the impact of renewable energy sources in livestock farming.

The simulation model, developed in 2022 by Faes et al. (Faes et al. 2022), estimates hourly heating loads of a specific pig barn by formulating and solving a heat balance equation for every compartment. In their previous work, the model has been compared to monthly gas use by means of validation, but not on an hourly level. In this work, an experimental set-up is proposed to measure hourly heating loads in a pig barn. The model's capability to predict hourly loads was assessed using these physical measurements.

Results indicate that while the model generally mirrors the behaviour in the hourly heat demands for the barn, discrepancies arise, particularly during warm weather conditions. These deviations highlight the need for further research to incorporate external factors such as weather conditions and precise animal occupation numbers into the model to enhance its accuracy. Despite these challenges, an improved version of the model could be used to estimate heating loads, offering valuable insights for integrating renewable energy sources and enhancing energy efficiency in intensive livestock farming.

Moving forward, expanding the model to encompass other livestock farms with varying characteristics will be crucial for its applicability across different contexts. By refining and validating the model through continued experimentation and data collection, it can serve as a valuable tool for simulating the impact of renewable energy technologies and optimizing energy management strategies in the livestock sector. Ultimately, such efforts contribute to mitigating the environmental footprint of intensive livestock farming and advancing sustainable agricultural practices.

NOMENCLATURE

The nomenclature should be located at the end of the text using the following format:

BES-model	building energy simulation model
LT	low temperature
HT	high temperature

Subscript

Floor	underfloor heating circuit at low temperature (LT)
Total	complete heating circuit at high temperature (HT)

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Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT 3.5 in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.